

CHARACTERISATION OF NON-CRIMP FABRIC DEFORMATION MECHANISMS DURING PREFORMING

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1 Introduction

The past 15 years have known an increasing interest in carbon composites based on non-crimp fabrics (NCF). Also known as multi-axial multiply fabrics (MMF), those composite reinforcements are cost effective and have high performance characteristics [1,2]. Thanks to the absence of crimp and to the through thickness stitching, the in-plane mechanical properties and the handling stability are enhanced. Combined with a resin transfer moulding (RTM) process it leads to promising composites with automation possibilities and increased size of parts for industries like aeronautic [3,4].

As the numerical simulation of composite forming processes becomes more and more significative in the design phase of the composite structures, there is a need of developing a dedicated methodology for the preforming simulation of non-crimp fabric reinforced composites.

Here we investigate on the deformability of dry non-crimp fabrics during preforming. Usual characterisation tests, like bias extension tests are performed and criticised. Then bias extension tests and hemispherical forming experiments are utilised to compare the involved mechanisms with those happening in woven fabrics. Finally, a specific finite element approach is proposed for the simulation of non-crimp fabric preforming.

2 Experimental characterisation

2.1 Bias extension tests for NCF

The in-plane shear behaviour of woven fabrics is usually characterised with two specific tests: the picture frame test and the bias extension test [5] (fig.1). Both tests give force and displacement data that can be processed in order to obtain the material shear properties. These are then implemented in finite element models. Here we use the bias extension test to observe in-plane shear behaviour of a non-crimp fabric.

Equation (1) gives the relation between displacement d and shear angle γ for a theoretical

bias extension test with a pin-jointed net (PJN) assumption. The yarns of the fabric are supposed to be inextensible and the rotation between warp and weft yarns is free.

$$\gamma(d) = \frac{\pi}{2} - \alpha = \frac{\pi}{2} - 2 \cdot \text{Arc cos} \left(\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} \left(1 - \frac{d}{L_o - L_a} \right) \right) \quad (1)$$

We compare the behaviour of a carbon fibre interlock fabric with a NCF described in table 1. The experimental curve for the interlock fabric fits the theory until a displacement of approximately 50 mm (fig.2). The pin-jointed net assumption is confirmed until that point when the tows begin to lock. For the NCF, the measured angle is clearly below the theory. During the whole experiment, the slope of the curve is almost constant and lower than the theoretical value. A difference of about 30 % is measured between theoretical and measured values. This difference is almost constant, meaning that slidings occur throughout the experiment. Other deformation mechanisms than pure in-plane shearing are happening. The difference may possibly be attributed to fibre sliding.

Optical measurements made at the bottom of the specimen reveal these slidings. The theoretical kinematics of the bias extension test is no more valid for this reinforcement; the assumption of non-sliding between the two plies is not verified.

2.2 Hemispherical drawing experiment

To go further, hemispherical drawing experiments are performed on 180 mm square fabric specimens (fig.3). The samples are fixed with a ring-shaped blank holder and drawn with a hemispherical punch with a 75 mm diameter. A grid of white markers is plotted on both sides of the reinforcement so as to measure the sliding between the warp and weft plies. The initial and final position of the markers is determined using a stereo-correlation software. The

position is determined in the frame of reference $(O, \bar{x}, \bar{y}, \bar{z})$ defined in figure 3. Then the sliding between the plies is calculated. The sliding is defined as the distance, projected onto the middle surface of the sample, between two markers initially opposed on both sides of the fabric. Slidings that reach almost 18 mm are observed at the transition zone between the hemispherical part and the plane base. This displacement appeared to be non negligible and involves modification on the plies position at the end of the preforming stage. At the edges of the sample, slidings lead to deteriorated zones with only one ply of fibre left. Fibres in one direction slide on fibres in the other direction but also on the stitches.

This experiment confirms that inter-ply slidings are non negligible when performing the preforming of a non-crimp fabric part over complex shape. This aspect should be included in the modelling process.

3 Tow sliding versus continuum finite element

3.1 Continuum media and macro-scale approach

Mapping methods have been the first to predict deformations of fabrics over simple shapes. Originally developed for plain weave fabrics having tow interlacing that prevents relative tow sliding, these techniques are based on a PJN assumption. But, as they don't account for boundary conditions and mechanical behaviour, these methods have limited accuracy. Then, the finite element method (FEM) which includes the mechanical behaviour and boundary conditions has been developed. This method allows the forming simulation of woven fabrics over complex shapes, usually with a macro-scale method for computing time considerations [6]. At a macro-scale, the fabric is considered as a continuum media allowing in-plane stretching, compression, bending and shear. But the tow sliding, tow compaction and stitch interaction can't be represented. With the spread of non-crimp fabrics, there is a need of understanding the exact deformation mechanisms involved and to characterise them for computing accurate finite element simulations [3,7].

For that purpose, a mesoscopic modelling of NCF draping has been proposed in [3]. Each tow making up the upper and lower plies is meshed with 3D solid elements and the stitches are meshed with bar elements. Contact and frictional sliding between the tows and stitches is treated. The modelling is closed

to physics at mesoscopic scale and it can describe all the slidings during forming. Nevertheless, the finite element model involves a large number of degree of freedom and above all a very large number of frictional contacts. Furthermore the 3D finite elements that are used for the tow cannot describe efficiently the bending of the tow. A hemispherical forming simulation based on this meso-modelling is presented but the slidings between the upper and lower plies are not highlighted by the simulation. When simulating the behaviour of the NCF studied here, sliding should be represented.

3.2 Finite element simulation

Accordingly, a macro-scale finite element model is proposed. This approach allows the simulation of non-crimp fabrics preforming with consideration to the specific deformation mechanisms underlined in paragraph 2. Indeed, it has been shown that slidings happen between warp and weft plies of the NCF. With a macro scale approach, this aspect can not be simulated when considering the fabric as a continuum media. Here, the two plies of the non-crimp fabric are modelled separately with shell finite elements based on a semi-discrete approach [6]. This system allows to simulate the slidings and remains efficient so as to simulate preforming experiment like the hemispherical drawing experiment (fig.4).

4 Conclusion

Deformation mechanisms occurring in dry non-crimp fabric preforming are different from those occurring with woven fabrics. Contrary to the interweaving that strictly held the tows of an interlock fabric, the stitches allow the relative displacement of the fibres of the considered non-crimp fabric. Consequently, a macro-scale finite element model is proposed. This approach allows the simulation and the prediction of inter-ply slidings of NCF.

Fig.1. Bias extension test on a carbon fibre interlock fabric (G1151 Hexcel composite).

Fig.2. Bias extension test results for an interlock fabric and a non-crimp fabric.

Fig.3. Sample of NCF after preforming (upper face)

Fig.4. Simulation of the hemispherical drawing of a NCF sample

	Type : NCF Loop Chain, HTS Fibers 12K, without Torsion. Stitching Pattern: Loop Chain per 5mm Polyester (PES 48dtex) 4 g/mz.	
warp ply	weft ply	

Table.1. Definition of the NCF use in the study.

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